

A Quadruple Helix Guide for Innovations

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

This guide introduces newcomers to the Quadruple Helix Model for multi-actor project proposal writing. It explains the model's purpose of fostering user-driven innovation through collaboration between public authorities, industry, academia, and citizens. The guide also provides practical examples and methods, such as Living Labs and Service Design, to illustrate how to effectively involve all stakeholders in the innovation process.

Benefits

This guide supports the inclusion in project proposals of effective collaboration among public authorities, industry, academia, and citizens, leading to practical solutions like Living Labs and Service Design that directly address user needs.

Practical recommendations

1. Start with Stakeholder Mapping:

- Identify and map all relevant stakeholders from the four sectors early in the process.
- Ensure each stakeholder understands their role and the value they bring to the project.

2. Utilize Co-Creation Sessions:

- Organize co-creation sessions to gather diverse perspectives and foster collaboration.
- Encourage open dialogue and active participation from all stakeholders.

3. Apply Living Labs:

- Implement Living Labs to test and refine solutions in real-life settings.

4. Incorporate Service Design:

- Follow the five steps of Service Design: Prepare, Explore, Understand, Improve, and Implement.
- Focus on user-centered design to ensure the solutions are practical and effective.

5. Leverage Various Methods:

- Use a mix of context adapted methods such as brainstorming, focus groups, and workshops to engage stakeholders.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

The active participation of, and focus on end-users

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Link to the material](#)

**right click to open*

Figure 1: Quadruple Helix Model

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